

FigS1. Sequential images of typical experiment

Sequential images obtained during a microfluidic experiment of WT strain exposed to an upshift from 0 to 220 mM glucose. Brightfield images indicate where the cell membrane is situated, in the green field Mig1-GFP is observed and in the red field images (Nrd1-RFP) the nucleus is localized.